

MOTIVATION, COMPETENCY AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR OF GOVERNMENT OFFICERS IN BALI PROVINCE IN GENDER PERSPECTIVE ON WORK SATISFACTION

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ABSTRACT

The research objective was to analyze motivation, competence, job satisfaction and OCB from a gender perspective, the influence of motivation, competence on job satisfaction and OCB. Research respondents were 388 people. Research data with primary data and questionnaires. Hypothesis testing uses SEM analysis with AMOS applications. The results of the study stated (1) from a gender perspective, female officials have lower work motivation, but have higher competence, job satisfaction, and OCB compared to male officials. (2) Motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction, (3) Motivation has a significant effect on OCB, (4) Competence has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction, (5) Competence has a significant effect on OCB (6) Job Satisfaction has a significant effect on OCB employees (7) Job satisfaction mediates and is significant on motivation and OCB, in mediating the influence of competence on OCB. Important findings from the research on developing the OCB dimensions, from five dimensions, namely altruism, civic virtue, thoroughness, politeness and sportsmanship, became seven dimensions by justifying and adding dimensions of accountability and transparency. Seen from a gender perspective, the dimensions of altruism, civic virtue, and accountability are more dominant in men, while women are more dominant in showing the dimensions of politeness, sportsmanship, thoroughness, and transparency.

Keywords: Gender, Competence Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

INTRODUCTION

Government efforts to improve the quality of public services can be made by implementing bureaucratic reforms aimed at creating good corporate governance. Bureaucratic reform is an effort to implement fundamental and comprehensive changes and reforms to the administration of government, including organizational aspects (institutional), governance (business process), and human resources/apparatus (General Guidelines for Bureaucracy Reform / PURB, 2008). It all starts with changes in the mindset, attitudes, and behavior of human resources so that they are more concerned with the organization rather than individual interests. Organizational performance can be measured in various dimensions, including environmental operation, finance, economics, marketing and competitiveness aspects (Mitra and Dalta, 2014; (Ueasangkomsate & Pornchaiwiseskul, 2019).

The success of individuals facing change is an organizational learning process. Organizational learning theory (Popper & Lipshitz, 1999, 2000; Riketta, 2002) requires the application of new cultural values and structural mechanisms, which ultimately change the perspective and role of individuals in organizations. The creation of a new organizational culture will change the behavior of the State Civil Apparatus, both in role behavior and extra-role behavior, in accordance with the principles of GCG (accountability, transparency, participation, and the rule of law} and values of continuous learning. Specific research on factors there is very few who encourage OCB in different contexts in public organizations (Alotaibi, 2001), according to (Pandey et al. 2007; Sharma et al. 2011), stating that employees in public organizations have higher OCB compared to employees in private organizations. Regarding OCB in public organizations becomes very important in order to be able to improve services to the community Ocampo (2018), in his empirical research, states that the development of the OCB dimension today is prolonged so that research is needed to develop OCB dimensions in accordance with the organizational form. It is stated that organizational citizenship behaviours affect organizational life in various aspects. These can be listed as the increase in the tendency of the workers to help each other, developing the sense of responsibility in workers and increase in the work success through citizenship behaviours. When the literature is reviewed, it becomes obvious that it has many benefits such as providing the sustainability of organizational and worker's performance, increasing the productivity of the workers and administration, achieving interpersonal harmony, enabling the adaptation to changes in organizational environment and making it possible to effectively use sources (Altintas, 2006; Ikinci, 2014).

The division of labor based on gender, often constructed rigidly, where economic activities tend to be classified according to gender. Some roles are seen as masculine or feminine. Nevertheless, the facts reinforce that the social roles of men and women are the result of the construction of society so that as a result, a role which in one place is considered masculine in another place is considered feminine. With the development of the roles played by women and men are no longer only determined by culture, but also by the dominant ideology at a time and by social, political, and economic factors. To develop and mature the various potentials that exist in women utilizing the same rights and opportunities as men as development resources.

Nevertheless, until now, there is still a perceived gender gap or gender bias in various development sectors so that the position and condition of women are not equal to men. Building gender equality and gender equity is difficult to do quickly because it still experiences obstacles

that stem from legitimacy, cultural construction, religious interpretation, and political policy. Gender equality is a process undertaken to deliver men and women dynamically to gain access, participation, control, and benefits in life activities both in the family, community, and nation and state (Puspitawati, 2012: 52).

The Provincial Government of Bali has implemented bureaucratic reform and good governance to create good corporate governance. All ASNs are always expected to have high motivation and always improve their competence to be able to carry out their duties properly, even officials from echelon one to echelon four are expected to coordinate for 24 hours. Officials are also required not only to behave in roles but are also required to behave extra roles, such as fostering underdeveloped villages, house renovation, greening, participating in social and religious activities, participating in sports activities, and other activities, where all of these activities are implemented outside working hours and aims to improve services and public welfare. The number of State Civil Apparatuses in Bali Province in 2018 was 6,896 people consisting of 4,227 men and 2,671 women. The number of officials in Bali Province was 941 people. The number of officials based on echelon is, for Echelon 1, Male is 1 person, Echelon 2, 44 people, Echelon 3 is 176 people, Echelon 4 is 393 people. While Echelon 1 for women is 0 people, Echelon 2 is 49 people, Echelon 3 is 238 people, and Echelon 4 is 653 people.

The achievement of excellent public services and the creation of good corporate governance requires the need for rapid change (Atmadja & Saputra, 2018; Atmadja, Saputra, & Manurung, 2019), where all employees, both men, and women can adapt effectively, by doing work outside the role or show OCB. The organization will function more effectively if employees contribute more than their formal tasks. Employees who work in organizations that have high performance have better OCB, compared to those who work in organizations that have poor performance (Bolino, 2002). For this reason, further research is needed on OCB. The differences in the results of research on motivation, competence, job satisfaction, OCB in a gender perspective and existing phenomena, it is necessary to do research again in the Government of Bali Province, so that it will have an impact on organizational performance. So with this study conducted to determine the effect of motivation, competence on job satisfaction, and organizational behavior of government officials in the Province of Bali from a Gender perspective.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Job Satisfaction of Officers in the Provincial Government of Bali

Motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction, and perseverance of an effort to achieve a goal (Robbin and Judge, 2008: 222). According to Hasibuan (2006: 143) argues that work motivation is providing the driving force that creates the excitement of one's work so that they want to work together, work effectively, and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve job satisfaction. Agung (2009) states that there is an influence of achievement needs, power needs, and affiliation needs on the job satisfaction of women entrepreneurs who are members of IWAPI Madiun. Saleem et al., (2010), examining cellular telecommunications service organizations in Pakistan, found that there was a positive and significant influence on employee

job satisfaction. (Job & Rafif 2011) examining the middle managers of several banks in Karachi, Pakistan found there was a positive influence on motivation for employee job satisfaction. (Benteaa & Anghelachea 2012) examining elementary to high school teachers in Romania found that teacher job satisfaction is influenced by achievement motivation and affiliate motivation. (Sunaryo & Suyono 2013) investigating the effect of motivation on job satisfaction and OCB employees in public organizations in Sragen, Central Java, found that there was a positive and significant effect of motivation on employee job satisfaction. Research conducted by (Rendy 1989; Zou 2007) states women has higher job satisfaction than men because women are happier with their work than men mainly due to differences in intrinsic and relational orientation towards work between the sexes. This can be the key to understanding why women have higher levels of job satisfaction, even when their working conditions are considered relatively unfavorable compared to men.

Motivation Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

Research that supports the positive and significant influence of motivation on OCB, among others, was conducted by Kim (2006) in his research finding that there is a positive and significant influence on motivation towards altruism and compliance, which are OCB dimensions. Pandey et al. (2007), who examined civil servants in the Northeastern United States, found that motivation had a positive and significant effect on interpersonal citizen behavior. Ariani (2012), who examined contract employees at Diponegoro University, found that there was a positive and significant effect on work motivation on OCB, and Sunaryo & Suyono (2013) examined the effect of motivation on job satisfaction and OCB employees at public organizations in Sragen, Central Java, found there was a significant influence on positive and significant motivation for OCB employees. Makvandi et al. (2017) found a positive and significant influence of work motivation on OCB teachers in Iran. Research conducted by Davis et al. (2006), which states that men have higher achievement motivation and power motivation than women and research conducted by Lamky (2007) which statesmen have achievement motivation and more affiliation motivation tall than women. Cooke (2003) states that female officials in China have lower work motivation than men because of the conventional socio-cultural construction, where women have low self-confidence, narrow-mindedness, lack of leadership charisma, fear of success, depending on men and family preferences are greater than preferences for their careers.

Competence Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Job Satisfaction of Officers in the Provincial Government of Bali

Female officials have higher competence compared to male officials, especially cognitive competencies and emotional intelligence competencies, while for social intelligence competencies, male officials are higher than female officials. Cognitive competence is an ability to think and analyze information and situations that lead or cause superior effectiveness or performance. The emphasis of this dimension is on systems thinking and pattern recognition of workers/employees in carrying out their work. Female officials have high cognitive competence because they have a higher ability to improve their quality based on reliable

information, understand the situation by analyzing problems logically and have better knowledge to get the job done than male officials.

This research is in line with research conducted by Ackfeldt & Coote (2000), examining retail employees, stating that there is a significant influence on employee professional development on job satisfaction. Begum (2005), in his research, stated that there was a significant influence of social competence on job satisfaction of employees of commercial banks in Bangladesh. Virk (2011) found emotional intelligence to have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and perceptions for employee success in telecommunications in North India. Orhan and Dincer (2012) found that there was a positive and significant influence on the competence of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction of employees of state-owned banks and private banks in Turkey. (Lu & Chen 2013) in his research found that there is a positive and significant influence on employees' emotional intelligence on job satisfaction of hospitality employees in China. Jayprakash & Amruth (2013) found that there was a positive and significant effect of competence on teacher job satisfaction in Teacher Educators Working in self-financing B.Ed. Indian colleges.

Competence Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Officers in the Provincial Government of Bali

Emotional intelligence competency is an ability to recognize, understand, and use emotional information about oneself that guides or causes superior effectiveness or performance (Jawad, Al, & Al-, 2019). The emphasis of this dimension is on the self-awareness and self-management competencies of workers/employees in the form of emotional self-awareness and emotional self-control in carrying out their work. Female officials have higher emotional intelligence competence than male officials because female officials have better abilities in restraining and managing emotions and are more optimistic in carrying out their duties.

The results of this study are not in accordance with research conducted by (Taylor 2012: 409; Porterfield 2005), which states that men have higher cognitive competence than women, whereas women dominantly own emotional intelligence competencies and social intelligence competencies. Female officials have a formal level of education at the S2, and S3 levels of education more than male officials and have a longer service life than male officials to be able to occupy echelon positions. The high level of formal education and the length of working time held by female officials makes cognitive competence, and emotional intelligence competencies possessed even higher. The high formal education and longer working period to be able to hold a position will increase the ability to think and analyze information and situations and be better able to control their emotions in doing work (Naeem, Mahdi, & Idan, 2019).

Job Satisfaction Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

Research that supports the positive and significant influence of job satisfaction on OCB is conducted among others (Konovsky and Organ 1996), which states that job satisfaction significantly influences the five dimensions of OCB professional employees and hospital administration. Bolon (1997) found that there was a positive and significant effect on job

satisfaction on OCB employees in Southeast American hospitals. (Ackfeldt and Cooté 2000) found a significant influence on job satisfaction on OCB retail employees. (Murphy and King 2002) examine work satisfaction and OCB on humanitarian service organizations in Australia, stating there is a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction on OCB. Begum (2005) states that there is a significant effect of job satisfaction on OCB employees of upper and middle-level commercial bank employees in Bangladesh. Chiu and Chen (2005) examined 24 electronics companies in Taiwan found that there was a positive and significant effect on intrinsic job satisfaction on OCB. Foote and Tang (2008) found a significant influence on the job satisfaction of manufacturing employees in the city of Pennsylvania, Mississippi, and in the village of Kentucky. Saepung et al. (2011) examined the effect of job satisfaction on OCB employees in 59 retail companies in Indonesia found there was a significant effect on job satisfaction on OCB. Avianti (2011) found that there was a significant effect of job satisfaction on OCB.

Job Satisfaction Mediates the Effect of Motivation and Competence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

The job satisfaction of female officials in the Provincial Government of Bali is higher compared to job satisfaction of male officials, especially for job satisfaction and satisfaction with coworkers, while satisfaction with superiors for male officials is higher than for female officials. Female officials are more satisfied with their work because they enjoy their current work more, are happy with the current level of work responsibilities, feel successful in their current work, and prefer other tasks related to their current work. Female officials have higher satisfaction with coworkers than male officials. This happens because female officials get a lot of support and assistance from colleagues with full responsibility for completing their duties, female officials who hold echelon positions are mostly over 50 years old and are nearing retirement, they tend to do work happily and more establish harmonious relationships with colleagues. The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Rendy (1989) and Zou (2007), which states women have higher job satisfaction than men because women are happier with their work than men mainly due to differences in intrinsic and relational orientation to work between the sexes. This can be the key to understanding why women have higher levels of job satisfaction, even when their working conditions are considered relatively unfavorable compared to men.

METHODOLOGY

The population in this study were officials in the Provincial Government of Bali, excluding 9th echelon officials totaling 940 people. The sampling technique used was proportionate stratified random sampling based on echelon and gender. The determination of the number of samples is based on the criteria of Isaac and Michael, with an error rate of 5 percent (Sugiono, 2013: 124). Based on the selection of samples that have been made, the total sample of 388 people consisted of 221 men and 167 women. The data collection method uses a questionnaire while the data analysis technique uses the structural equation modeling (SEM) using AMOS 20 software and testing is done with a single test to find out the significant level of job satisfaction roles in mediating motivation and competence towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior

and the VAF test to determine the magnitude of the mediating role of job satisfaction in mediating the influence of motivation and competence on OCB.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Motivation Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Job Satisfaction of Officers in the Provincial Government of Bali

Work motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates the excitement of one's work, so they want to work together, work effectively, and are integrated with all their efforts to achieve job satisfaction (Hasibuan, 2006: 143). Motivation is a mental condition that encourages action or activities and gives strength (energy) that leads to the achievement of needs, giving satisfaction, or reducing imbalances. The motivation in this study is assessed from the need for achievement (need for achievement), need for power (need for power), and need for affiliation (need for affiliation).

Based on Figure 5.1 and obtained the value of Standardized Regression Weight Direct Effect motivation on job satisfaction of 0.067 with a significance of 0.019, because the significance value of $0.019 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. This means that if the work motivation of officials is high, then job satisfaction is also high. Descriptive research results also state that official work motivation is classified as good criteria, and job satisfaction is also classified as good criteria. The better the work motivation of officials, the better job satisfaction.

Motivation Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

Motivation is a condition that encourages or becomes the cause of someone doing an action/activity, which takes place consciously. This understanding starts from the main principle that someone only does an activity that is fun to do (Nawawi, 2007: 96). Moorman (1991) said that OCB should be considered as an important part of a job because OCB is an important part of spontaneous and innovative behavior, which is a way or tool towards an effective organization. If employees are highly motivated, they will have spontaneous and innovative behavior for the progress of the organization without demanding rewards.

The value of the Standardized Regression Weight Direct Effect motivation on organizational citizenship behavior is 0.122 with a significance of 0.022 because the significance value is $0.022 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that motivation has a positive and significant effect on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. This means that the higher the work motivation, the higher the desire of employees to do organizational citizenship behavior for the betterment of the organization. Descriptive research results indicate that work motivation and OCB officials are included in good criteria, this reinforces the results of research if employees have good work motivation, the better it is to do OCB.

Competence Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Job Satisfaction of Officers in the Provincial Government of Bali

Boyatzis (2008) argues that: competence is an essential characteristic of someone who guides or causes outstanding effectiveness and performance. Zurnali (2010) states that employees who have competence will not produce optimal consumer-oriented or other stakeholder behavior if workers are not given freedom, freedom, and independence in controlling their work, which includes core decisions regarding work, time frame, or content related to the substance of the decision. If an employee has a high level of competence, he will have a high level of job satisfaction as well, because by having competency simultaneously satisfaction with his work will arise in the employee.

Based on Figure 5.1, the value of the Standardized Regression Weight Direct Effect competence on job satisfaction is 0.636 with a significance of 0,000, because the significance value is $0,000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. This means that the higher the competency, the higher job satisfaction. Descriptive research results indicate competency and satisfaction of officials classified as good criteria, and this strengthens the results of the study, if employees have good competence, then job satisfaction will be good.

Competence Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Officers in the Provincial Government of Bali.

According to Antariksa (2007), in general, competence itself can be understood as a combination of skills (skills), personal attributes, and knowledge (knowledge) that is reflected through work behavior (job behavior) that can be observed, measured and evaluated. Competence is a requirement that underlies an individual or someone to show high performance in carrying out their work in order to be able to perform superiorly as a form of extra-role behavior (OCB).

Based on Figure 5.1, the value of the Standardized Regression Weight Direct Effect competence on OCB is 0.758 with a significance of 0.000, because the significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that competence has a positive and significant effect on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. This means that the higher the competency, the extra-role behavior (OCB) will increase. The result of descriptive research shows that the competencies and OCB of the officials are classified as good criteria, this shows that if the employee has good competency, the better it is to do OCB.

Job Satisfaction Has a Positive and Significant Impact on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

Azash et al. (2011) state that job satisfaction is a perceived relationship between what is expected with what is obtained from one's work. If someone receives what he expects from work, of course, he will do work with a feeling of pleasure and satisfaction. On the other hand, if someone is unable to meet the expectations of the job, dissatisfaction will emerge. Employees who are satisfied with the role are more likely to talk positively about the organization, help coworkers, and make their work performance exceed normal estimates. More than that, satisfied employees are more obedient to the call of duty because they want to repeat their

positive experiences (Robbins, 2008). Employees who have high job satisfaction tend to do OCB.

Based on Figure 5.1, the value of Standardized Regression Weight Direct Effect obtained job satisfaction for OCB of 0.255 with a significance of 0,000, because the significance value of 0,000 <0.05, it can be concluded that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. This means that the higher job satisfaction they have, the extra-role behavior (OCB) will increase. Descriptive research results indicate that job satisfaction and OCB officials are classified as good criteria. This shows that if employees are satisfied with their work, the better it is to do OCB.

Job Satisfaction Mediates the Effect of Motivation and Competence on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

Based on Figure 5.1 shows that motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, and job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. To see the role of job satisfaction mediating motivation and competence with OCB using the Sobel test and the VAF test. Sobel test results obtained t value for the role of job satisfaction mediating the relationship of motivation with OCB of 2.6151 > 1.96 with a significance of 0.004 <0.05 indicating that job satisfaction mediates the influence of motivation with OCB. Sobel test results for the role of job satisfaction mediate the relationship with OCB competence obtained t value of 3.371 > 1.96 with a significance of 0.0003 <0.05, it can be concluded that job satisfaction mediates the effect of competence with OCB. Because the value of direct influence is greater than the indirect effect, it can be said that job satisfaction partially mediates motivation and competence with OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali.

The VAF test shows that the role of job satisfaction is only 14.35 percent in mediating the influence of motivation on OCB, and 16.11 percent mediating the effect of competence on OCB. (Sunaryo and Suyono 2013; Mushtaq et al. 2014) examining the banking sector in Pakistan found that job satisfaction partially mediates motivation with OCB. An employee, if he has high work motivation and is satisfied with his work, superiors, and coworkers, tends to do OCB.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, there are some conclusions in this study, which are as follows. From a gender perspective, female officials have lower work motivation but have higher competence, job satisfaction, and OCB compared to male officials. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. A public official, if he has high work motivation, his job satisfaction will increase. Motivation has a positive and significant influence on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali. If public officials have high work motivation, then more and more do OCB. Competence has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction of officials in the Provincial Government of Bali, and this means that the higher the competency of a public official, the more job satisfaction will be increased. Competence has a positive and significant

effect on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali, and this means that the higher the competency a public official has, the more OCB will do. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB officials in the Bali Provincial Government, and this means that if job satisfaction increases, the more OCBs will be carried out. Job satisfaction mediates partially and significantly the effect of motivation on OCB and the effect of competency on OCB officials in the Provincial Government of Bali, this means that motivation and competence influence directly or indirectly through job satisfaction with OCB.

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